

Medical Hypothesis: Caffeic Acid

Domina Petric, MD

Clinical pharmacology and toxicology

University Hospital Center Split, Croatia

ABSTRACT

Caffeic acid, which is pharmacologically active compound of many traditional medicinal herbs such as *Echinacea purpurea* and *Sambucus Formosana Nakai*, might be a potent molecule for the treatment of COVID-19, especially if pared with Fe^{3+} ions (caffeic acid Fe^{3+} chelate) or other ions (MoO_4^{2-} and PO_4^{3-} chelates), because antiviral activity of caffeic acid increases upwards of 100-fold by the addition of cations (Fe^{3+}) and anionic molecules (molybdate, phosphate). It has also been reported that caffeic acid, which exhibits antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial and antiproliferative properties, has antioxidant property in normal cells and pro-oxidant property in cancer cells, what leads to pro-oxidant-mediated oxidative DNA damage and its downstream signaling induces apoptotic cancer cell death. Theoretically, caffeic acid and its derivatives have characteristics of a perfect chemotherapeutic agent that is protective for normal cells and destructive for cancer cells.

Keywords: caffeic acid; COVID-19; cancer

INTRODUCTION

Echinacea purpurea (Asteraceae) is a perennial medicinal herb with important immuno-stimulatory and anti-inflammatory properties, especially the alleviation of cold symptoms. Different classes of secondary metabolites of the plant such as alkamides, caffeic acid derivatives, polysaccharides, and glycoproteins are believed to be biologically and pharmacologically active¹. *Echinacea purpurea* has both antibacterial (against *Streptococcus pyogenes*, *Haemophilus influenzae*, *Legionella pneumophila*...) and antiviral properties (mostly against respiratory viral infections, including coronaviruses) and it is suitable for relieving symptoms of

respiratory tract infections²⁻¹⁰. *Echinacea purpurea* medicinal preparations can be used for prevention, in the treatment of early phase and in mild respiratory infections. It has been reported in an *in vitro* study that *Echinacea purpurea* had antiviral activity against SARS-CoV and MERS coronaviruses¹¹.

Sambucus nigra products (Sambucol) have antiviral properties against different strains of influenza virus. Sambucol Elderberry Extract and its formulations activate the healthy immune system by increasing inflammatory cytokine production. Standardized elderberry liquid extract possesses antimicrobial activity against both Gram-positive bacteria of *Streptococcus pyogenes* and group C and G

Streptococci, and the Gram-negative bacterium *Branhamella catarrhalis* in liquid cultures. *Sambucus Formosana Nakai* stem ethanol extract displayed the strong anti-HCoV-NL63 (human coronavirus NL63) potential¹²⁻¹⁵.

HYPOTHESIS I

Caffeic acid, which is pharmacologically active compound of many medicinal herbs such as *Echinacea purpurea* and *Sambucus Formosana Nakai*, might be a potent molecule for the treatment of COVID-19, especially if paired with Fe^{3+} ions (caffeic acid Fe^{3+} chelate) or other ions (MoO_4^{2-} and PO_4^{3-} chelates), because antiviral activity of caffeic acid increases upwards of 100-fold by the addition of cations (Fe^{3+}) and anionic molecules (molybdate, phosphate). Caffeic acid and its derivatives may be used against the spread of SARS-CoV-2 and should be tested as prophylaxis and treatment of COVID-19.

HYPOTHESIS II

It has been reported that caffeic acid, which exhibits antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial and antiproliferative properties, has antioxidant property in normal cells and pro-oxidant property in cancer cells, what leads to pro-oxidant-mediated oxidative DNA damage and its downstream signaling induces apoptotic cancer cell death. Theoretically, caffeic acid and its derivatives have characteristics of a perfect chemotherapeutic agent that is protective for normal cells and destructive for cancer cells.

EVIDENCE SUPPORT

Hypothesis I

It has been found in a study that antiviral activity of caffeic acid increases upwards of 100-fold by the addition of cations (Fe^{3+}) and anionic molecules (molybdate, phosphate)¹⁶.

Kumar and coworkers examined in a study the binding potential of Withaferin-A (Wi-A), Withanone (Wi-N) (active withanolides of Ashwagandha) and Caffeic Acid Phenethyl Ester (CAPE, bioactive ingredient of propolis) to a highly conserved protein, M^{pro} of SARS-CoV-2. Authors found that Wi-N and CAPE, but not Wi-A, bind to the substrate-binding pocket of SARS-CoV-2 M^{pro} with efficacy and binding energies equivalent to an already claimed N3 protease inhibitor. Similar to N3 inhibitor, Wi-N and CAPE were interacting with the highly conserved residues of the proteases of coronaviruses. The binding stability of these molecules was further analyzed using molecular dynamics simulations. The binding free energies calculated using MM/GBSA for N3 inhibitor, CAPE and Wi-N were also comparable. Data presented by the authors predicted that these natural compounds may possess the potential to inhibit the functional activity of SARS-CoV-2 protease which is an essential protein for virus survival¹⁷. Adem and coworkers screened a library of 27 caffeic-acid derivatives against 5 proteins of SARS-CoV-2 by using Molegro Virtual Docker 7 to obtain the binding energies and interactions between compounds and SARS-

CoV-2 proteins. The results uncovered khainaoside C, 6-O-Caffeoylarbutin, khainaoside B, khainaoside C and vitexfolin A as potent modulators of COVID-19 possessing more binding energies than nelfinavir against COVID-19 M^{pro}, Nsp15, SARS-CoV-2 spike S2 subunit, spike open state and closed state structure. Calceolarioside B was identified as pan inhibitor, showing strong molecular interactions with all proteins except SARS-CoV-2 spike glycoprotein closed state¹⁸. Khalil and Tazeddinova published a review on the most highlighted polyphenolic compounds present in up-to-date literature and their specific antiviral perceptive properties that might enhance the body immunity facing COVID-19, and other viral infectious diseases. Authors concluded that caffeic acid and its derivatives have uncountable antiviral activities that may be used against the spread of COVID-19 and its related symptoms¹⁹.

Hypothesis II

Caffeic acid (3, 4-dihydroxy cinnamic acid) exhibits antioxidant, anti-inflammatory and antiproliferative properties. It has been reported that caffeic acid possesses antioxidant property in normal cells and pro-oxidant property in cancer cells. This pro-oxidant-mediated oxidative DNA damage and its downstream signaling induces apoptotic cancer cell death²⁰. In a study, designed to evaluate the anticancer effect of caffeic acid on HT-1080 human fibrosarcoma cell line, researchers observed increased oxidative

DNA damage and apoptotic morphological changes in caffeic acid-treated groups, suggesting that caffeic acid exhibits potent anticancer effect in HT-1080 cell line, and that it may be used as an anticancer agent²¹. Caffeic acid phenethyl ester (CAPE), extracted from propolis, was proven to inhibit colon cancer cells. Caffeic acid p-nitrophenethyl ester (CAPE-pNO₂), a derivative of CAPE, was determined to be an anti-platelet agent and a protector of myocardial ischaemia. CAPE-pNO₂ showed stronger cytotoxic activity than CAPE: it induced apoptosis in HT-29 cells by up-regulating P53, cleaved-caspase-3, Bax, P38 and CytoC. CAPE-pNO₂ also up-regulated P21Cip1 and P27Kip1 and down-regulated CDK2 and cMyc to promote cell cycle arrest in G₀/G₁. In xenograft studies, CAPE-pNO₂ remarkably suppressed tumor growth dose dependently and decreased the expression of VEGF (vascular endothelial growth factor) in tumor tissue, while HE (hematoxylin and eosin) staining showed that no observable toxicity was found in the heart, liver, kidney and spleen. Metabolites of CAPE-pNO₂ in HT-29 cells and organs were detected. In conclusion, para-nitro may enhance the anticancer effect of CAPE by inhibiting colon cancer cell viability, inducing apoptosis and cell cycle arrest via the P53 pathway, and inhibiting tumor growth and reducing tumor invasion by decreasing the expression of VEGF²².

A study, designed to investigate the effects of anti-diabetic drug metformin and caffeic acid

alone and in combination to treat an aggressive metastatic human cervical HTB-34 (ATCC CRL-1550) cancer cell line, showed that caffeic acid at concentration of 100 μ M, unlike metformine at 10 mM, activated 5'-adenosine monophosphate-activated protein kinase (AMPK). Caffeic acid contributed to the fueling of mitochondrial tricarboxylic acids (TCA) cycle with pyruvate by increasing Pyruvate Dehydrogenase Complex (PDH) activity, while metformin promoted glucose catabolism to lactate. In conclusion, caffeic acid mediated reprogramming of glucose processing through TCA cycle via oxidative decarboxylation. The increased oxidative stress, as a result of caffeic acid treatment, sensitized cancer cells and, acting on cell biosynthesis and bioenergetics, made HTB-34 cells more susceptible to metformin and successfully inhibited neoplastic cells. Authors concluded that the combination of metformin and caffeic acid to suppress cervical carcinoma cells by two independent mechanisms may provide a promising approach to cancer treatment²³. *In vitro* and *in vivo* studies have demonstrated the anticarcinogenic activity of caffeic acid against hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC), which are associated with its antioxidant and pro-oxidant capacity, and attributed to its chemical structure that has free phenolic hydroxyls, the number and position of OH in the catechol group and the double bond in the carbonic chain. Caffeic acid can act by preventing the production of reactive oxygen

species, inducing DNA oxidation of cancer cells, as well as reducing tumor cell angiogenesis, blocking STATS (transcription factor and signal translation 3), and suppressing collagen IV metalloproteases, namely MMP2 and MMP9²⁴.

PROSPECTIVE

In order to prove or refute these two hypotheses, more preclinical, including *in silico* studies, are necessary to determine which caffeic acid derivative(s) has the most potent antiviral effect (hypothesis 1), and which derivative(s) has the most potent anti-cancerogenic effect (hypothesis 2). Next step is to conduct animal studies in order to prove or refute antiviral and chemotherapeutic effects of different caffeic acid derivatives on animals as well as to determine toxicological properties. Finally, clinical trials should be conducted with a goal to explore the prophylactic and therapeutic potential of caffeic acid (derivatives) in COVID-19 and other viral or bacterial respiratory illnesses, as well as chemotherapeutic efficacy of caffeic acid (derivatives) alone or in combination with standard chemotherapy in different types of cancer, depending on the previously obtained results from *in vitro* and animal studies. In summary, caffeic acid (derivatives) is a promising molecule and more research on this issue might be both relevant and feasible.

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